

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT POSTOPERATIVE NAUSEA AND VOMITING.

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ABSTRACT

Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) are disturbing and show adverse events in anesthesia and surgery. These effects prolong recovery time, delay patient discharge, and increase hospital costs. PONV is one of the 2 main disadvantages of general anesthesia after the surgery in the first 24 hours. The origin of postoperative nausea and vomiting after surgery performed under general anesthesia is not entirely clear, but it is probably multifactorial. PONV is influenced by the patient's own factors (age, gender, obesity, diabetes, pregnancy), preoperative (premedication, anxiety, diet), intraoperative (anesthetics, intubation, aerophagia, intraoperative dehydration, high doses of neostigmine, use of N₂O, time of surgery) and using of opiates. The effectiveness of various antiemetics has been studied for the prevention and treatment of PONV in surgical patients. Glucocorticoids are well known for their analgesic, anti-inflammatory, immune-modulating, and antiemetic effects. Ondansetron is the most prophylactic serotonin subtype 3 antagonists in our daily clinical practice for the prevention of PONV after surgery.

Keywords: anesthesia, dexamethasone, ondansetron, PONV.

INTRODUCTION

What is a PONV?

Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) are a common problem after general anesthesia with an incidence 20-30% of all surgical patients. PONV remains a common cause of morbidity within 24 hours after surgery. The etiology of PONV is multifactorial, involving anesthetic agents, the type of surgery together with patient factors. This is a complex reflex involving multiple inputs via diverse receptor pathways which are integrated in the brainstem emetic center. [1] It is important to recognize

that nausea is a common complaint. Nausea is a subjective sensation usually described as a sensation that precedes vomiting, often patients feel as if they are ready all the time for vomiting. Conscious awareness of subconscious stimulation in an area of the medulla closely related to or part of the vomiting center. The known causes are :

- (1) Irritant impulses coming from the gastrointestinal tract
- (2) Impulses originating in the lower brain associated with motion sickness or
- (3) Impulses from the cerebral cortex to initiate vomiting

gastrointestinal tract, from the vagal and sympathetic nerves to the lower vagal tract, through the spinal nerves to the diaphragm and abdominal muscles. [5]

What are the risk factors for PONV?

There is a complex series of etiological factors where we mention here the most important: anesthetics, patient, surgery, postoperative condition. [2, 6] We can analyze first the factors related to anesthesia. We can count all: Taking volatile anesthetics over 2 hours: Use of N2O: Use of electrolyte solutions versus macromolecules: Use of opioids at the end of anesthesia and after it: Use of anticholinesterases for discouragement. And intravenous anesthetic agents are associated with different degrees of spice, especially thiopental natrum, etomidate are known to cause PONV. New agents like Propofol are less emetogenic. Using of inhaled anesthetic agents, we increase a lot the risk for PONV: Nitric oxide is known for its emetogenic effect first which is caused by stimulation of central opioid receptors, intestinal distension and increased pressure in the middle ear. Meanwhile, the new isoflurane, halothane, enflurane volatile agents, apart from the fact that they have a lower incidence, have no differences between them on clinical significance. Unstable anesthetics are the leading cause of PONV within the first two hours after surgery. The emetogenic effect is dose dependent. There are no differences between isoflurane, sevoflurane and desflurane. Replacement with propofol of an unstable anesthetic reduces the risk by about 19%. It is less emetogenic than volatile agents. The effects of N2O and volatile agents are additional (independent). Increasing the duration by 30 min increases the risk of PONV by 60%. Muscle relaxants themselves do not cause vomiting but their antidote as neostigmine is known to increase muscle tone thus increasing the risk for PONV. Opioids stimulate PONV stimulate chemoreceptors in the Trigger area in the Postrema Area.

Opioid saving strategies reduce the incidence of risk factors for PONV. [6-10]

The risk for PONV related with patient factors are: Sexy -Female (Adult women have a 2 to 4 risk than adult men.

This is related to female hormones and is especially pronounced during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle):

Age- Children (The highest incidence is age 6-16 years. Also, children have 2 times higher risk than adults):

Non-smokers (Regular smokers are 1.8 times less likely to do PONVs than non-smokers):.

Previous history of postoperative vomiting:

Travel diseases: Obesity (adipose tissue mass serves as a warehouse for anesthetics that undergo redistribution emphasizing their negative effects as well as PONV). [7, 8]

An important role on risk of PONV played and factors related to surgery:

Extending the intervention:

Type of surgery: Gastric aspirations and placed of nasogastric tube: the type of surgery-Major abdominal surgeries and gynecological procedures: Laparoscopy, Cholecystectomy, Middle Ear Surgery, Thyroid Surgery, Plastic Surgery.

PONV in laparoscopy affect till 70% of patients and comes from insufflation of gas in the abdomen increases pressure on the vagus nerve [11].

The most emetogenic procedures are laparoscopy, adult strabismus surgery, middle ear surgery, tonsillectomy, adnexectomy.

Nausea and vomiting are among the main causes that bring the patient back to the hospital. They occur in 10-80% and are a worrying problem for the patient and the doctor.[12]

Apfel score

Apfel has proposed a simple scoring system to predict the incidence for PONV (tab 1)

Apfel Score to Predict PONV

Risk factors	Points
Female sex	1
Non-smoker	1
History of PONV/ motion sickness	1
Postoperative opioids	1
Total	0-4

Score	Probability of PONV
0 points	10%
1 point	20%
2 points	40%
3 points	60%
4 points	80%

Evidence	Risk factors
Positive overall	Female sex (B1) History of PONV or motion sickness (B1) Nonsmoking (B1) Younger age (B1) General versus regional anesthesia (A1) Use of volatile anesthetics and nitrous oxide (A1) Postoperative opioids (A1) Duration of anesthesia (B1) Type of surgery (cholecystectomy, laparoscopic, gynecological) (B1)
Conflicting	ASA physical status (B1) Menstrual cycle (B1) Level of anesthetist's experience (B1) Muscle relaxant antagonists (A2)
Disproven or of limited clinical relevance	BMI (B1) Anxiety (B1) Nasogastric tube (A1) Supplemental oxygen (A1) Perioperative fasting (A2) Migraine (B1)

PONV = postoperative nausea and vomiting; BMI = body mass index; MS = motion sickness.

Pharmacological treatment of PONV

First line of antiemetics divided in 3 groups: 1) Serotonin antagonists (ondansetron) 2) Corticosteroids (dexamethasone) 3) Dopamine antagonists (droperidol). These groups have similar effects in reducing PONV. They have different mechanisms of action and can be combined.

Serotonin antagonists, 5HT₃, which represent the class of drugs with the greatest power of antiemetic action. This class includes ondansetron, granisetron, dolasetron and tropisetron. To prevent postoperative vomiting, they are administered at the end of anesthesia at a dose of 4 mg ondansetron, or 0.5 to 1 mg granisetron intravenously. Ondansetron is used in chemotherapy to reduce nausea and vomiting. Plasma half-life 4 hours. Most effective when given at the end of the operation. It is the most effective antiemetic (GOLD STANDARD). Side effects: headache, constipation, QT prolongation

Corticosteroids, Dexamethasone, in addition to its anti-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory effects, also manifests good antiemetic action. Unlike other antiemetics, its action starts late, therefore its intravenous administration is estimated to be done not less than 1.5 to 2 hours before the end of the operation and extubation of the patient. The antiemetic dose is 4 to 8 mg. Recent studies are increasingly using higher doses of dexamethasone 8 mg IV than the minimum effective dose of 4 to 5 mg. A meta-analysis evaluating dose-dependent analgesic effects of dexamethasone found that doses > 0.1 mg / kg are an effective aid in multimodal strategies to reduce postoperative pain and opioid consumption. Methylprednisolone 40 mg IV is effective in preventing late PONV.

Droperidol, D₂-antagonist, Butyrophenone group, is known for its antiemetic properties, as well as other neuroleptics. The antiemetic dose is 0.5 to 1.5 mg at the end of the intervention. The plasma half-life is 3 hours. It has a disadvantage over other medications as it can delay the patient waking up after anesthesia, anxiety, dystonia, torsade de point

Neurokinin Antagonists Substance P binds to NK1 receptors found in vagal afferents in the gastrointestinal tract. Located near the center of vomiting

APREPITANT - the first drug approved for clinical use by the FDA. Superior to prevent vomiting but not nausea. Dose = 40 mg. 40-hour plasma half-life

Aprepitant is rarely used in PONV due to its high cost. The newest antagonist receptors are CASOPITANT and ROLAPITAN.

Second line of antiemetics:

Metoclopramide (primperan) is a widely used antiemetic. It is injected intravenously at a dose of 10 mg before the end of anesthesia. The dose may be repeated if nausea or vomiting occur.

Dimenhydrinate is an antihistamine like promethazine and cyclizine. It has a number of side effects such as drowsiness, dry mucous membranes, visual disturbances, urinary retention.

Scopolamine is a cholinergic antagonist commonly used in 'motion sickness' (driving, seasickness)

Antiemetic effects have and some substances such as: cholinergic, ephedrine, some antihistamines or generally neuroleptics. Due to the cardiovascular effects or inhibition of the CNS, their use remains very limited in anesthesia wards. Peripheral opioid antagonist reduce the severity of nausea in the late postoperative period without affecting the central analgesic effects of opioids. Alvimopan appears to work by reducing postoperative and opioid-induced ileus Opioid-induced intestinal dysfunction. The mean plasma propofol concentration associated with an antiemetic response was 343 ng / mL, which is much lower than the concentration range associated with general anesthesia (3-6 mcg / mL) or sedation (1-3 mcg / mL). Propofol, in small doses (20 mg as needed), can be used in TIVA therapy for induction and maintenance of anaesthesia. Antiemetic effects have and alfa 2 agonist with representant Clonidine and dexmedetomidine. They are significant but with a weak and short-lived effect as an anti-inflammatory effect.

CONCLUSION

What should you do in the future? From the information of literature and our experience we suggested first of all to determine who are the risk groups for PONV according to Apfel scoring system. The Apfel scoring system is worth for prophylactic antiemetic to patients at high risk for PONV. The health system all the time need from us to evaluate the cost-effectiveness ratio in PONV management strategies. We must stabilize in preanesthetic protocol all the factors that lead to increased risk for PONV. The anesthetists must determine which are the most effective antiemetic drugs used alone or in combination for prophylaxis together with the best treatment for PONV in patients with or without prophylaxis and the optimal dose and for prophylaxis.

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